

Transitioning O-RAN toward Post-Quantum Security: A Layered Architecture, Performance Estimation, and Migration Strategies

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Abstract—Open Radio Access Networks (O-RAN) introduce flexibility and multi-vendor interoperability through open and standardized interfaces. The emergence of programmable RAN Intelligent Controllers (RICs), along with the ability to deploy third-party applications as xApps and rApps, further accelerates innovation. However, these advancements also expand the attack surface of 6G infrastructures and introduce significant new security challenges. As quantum computing threatens classical cryptography, O-RAN security must evolve toward quantum-resilient mechanisms. This article outlines a layered migration roadmap for integrating Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC) and hybrid schemes into O-RAN’s identity, control, and runtime layers. Building on O-RAN Alliance Work Group 11 and GSMA post-quantum telco network task force guidelines, we estimate the relative cost and performance trade-offs of classical, hybrid, and PQC-only protections across key interfaces. The results show that hybrid integration provides near-term quantum resistance with moderate overhead, while full PQC deployment requires architectural adaptation. The proposed approach offers a standards-aligned path toward secure, interoperable, and energy-aware O-RAN evolution for 6G.

Index Terms—Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC), O-RAN Security, Hybrid Cryptography, Quantum-Safe 6G, Performance Evaluation.

I. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

Open Radio Access Networks (O-RAN) are reshaping mobile infrastructure by separating hardware and software and enabling multi-vendor, cloud-native deployments [1]. The key objectives of O-RAN include the promotion of open and standardized interfaces, the integration of intelligent network automation into the RAN, the reduction of capital and operational expenditure and the virtualization of network functions to eliminate the dependency on proprietary hardware [2]. The O-RAN Alliance defines the architecture and interfaces that realize this vision, including the Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) framework, the Non-Real-Time (non-RT) and Near-Real-Time (near-RT) RAN Intelligent Controllers (RICs), and a disaggregated next-generation NodeB (gNB) composed of the O-RAN Central Unit (O-CU), O-RAN Distributed Unit (O-DU), and O-RAN Radio Unit (O-RU). These components are interconnected via standardized open interfaces, such as O1, O2, A1, E2, and the Open Fronthaul (O-FH) interface, as illustrated in Figure 1. This openness increases the number of trust boundaries and exposes control,

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user, synchronization, and management (CUS&M) planes to new attack surfaces [1], [3]–[5].

Fig. 1. Logical Architecture of O-RAN

Current O-RAN deployments rely on classical public-key cryptography embedded in TLS, IPsec, OAuth 2.0, and PKI infrastructures [6], [7]. OAuth-based authorization also enables xApp interactions with RIC APIs, as well as for inter-xApp communication [8], via JSON Web Tokens (JWTs) signed with digital signatures. These mechanisms are vulnerable to quantum computers: Shor’s algorithm breaks RSA and Elliptic-curve Cryptography (ECC), and *store-now-decrypt-later* attacks already endanger recorded traffic. Telecom operators must therefore migrate toward *quantum-safe* protection for credentials, session establishment, and software integrity. NIST has standardized ML-KEM and ML-DSA as the primary Post-Quantum (PQ) key-establishment and signature schemes [9], forming the cornerstone of PQ-security for 6G networks.

The standardization landscape remains incomplete. O-RAN Alliance Work Group 11’s (WG11) Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC) Security Technical Report [6] maps cryptographic dependencies but does not yet define PQ-capable certificate

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF PQC INTEGRATION APPROACHES IN O-RAN AND TELECOM SYSTEMS

Approach	O-RAN Alignment	Layered Architecture	Protocol-Level Integration	System-Level Impact Analysis	Migration Roadmap
Aydeger et al. [12]	Partial	No	Yes	No	No
Q-RAN [13]	Yes	No	Yes	Partial	Partial
O-RAN WG11 PQC TR [6]	Yes	No	No	No	No
GSMA PQTN [10]	Partial	No	No	No	Yes
Our Work	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

models, hybrid-negotiation policies, or latency budgets for PQ operations on timing-critical control loops. GSMA PQTN guidelines [10] outline a high-level migration process, while ETSI QSC [11] and 3GPP SA3 still lack operational guidance for integrating PQC into RAN performance constraints.

Prior work has examined conceptual mappings of PQC to O-RAN interfaces [12] and, more recently, the Q-RAN architecture [13] demonstrated a prototype using PQ-TLS, PQ-IPsec, and PQ certificate authorities. However, these studies primarily focus on protocol-level integration or isolated experimental validation, and provide limited quantitative insight into the computational, latency, and energy overheads of PQ vs. hybrid cryptography across O-RAN layers. Moreover, they do not offer a unified architectural framework that maps PQC adoption across O-RAN functional domains or supports system-level deployment reasoning.

To further clarify the positioning of this paper, Table I provides a qualitative comparison with existing PQC integration approaches in O-RAN and telecom systems.

This article complements existing WG11 and GSMA PQTN initiatives by providing a system-level perspective on PQC integration in O-RAN, enabling reasoning about where and how PQC can be introduced without violating timing and interoperability constraints. While current standardization efforts identify cryptographic dependencies and outline migration principles, they do not provide a structured mapping of PQC across O-RAN layers or quantify system-level trade-offs.

To address these gaps, we present: (i) a layered trust architecture aligned with O-RAN specifications, mapping PQC and hybrid mechanisms to identity, control, and runtime domains; (ii) a comparative analysis of classical, PQ, and hybrid cryptography across these layers; and (iii) normalized estimates of their computational, memory, and latency costs based on recent PQ performance measurements.

II. SECURITY CHALLENGES IN QUANTUM-RESILIENT O-RAN

PQ migration in O-RAN is constrained not by cryptography but by system-level properties, including timing determinism, software lifecycle velocity, and heterogeneous hardware budgets. Table II summarizes the main system-level challenges that emerge from O-RAN's open and disaggregated design [5]. They span software trust, timing determinism, lifecycle agility, resource variability, and multi-vendor coordination, factors that jointly define the limits of quantum-safe adoption and motivate gradual, hybrid integration rather than full replacement.

TABLE II
SYSTEM-LEVEL CHALLENGES AFFECTING PQC MIGRATION IN O-RAN

Challenge	Implications for O-RAN and PQC Adoption
Expanded trust surface	xApps and rApps are externally sourced software components integrated through open APIs. Each introduces new certificate chains, deployment pipelines, and potential compromise points within the SMO and RIC layers.
Real-time control	The Near-RT RIC must maintain deterministic control loops between 10 ms and 1 s. PQC operations, especially lattice-based key encapsulation and signatures, add latency and jitter that may violate closed-loop deadlines.
Lifecycle trust	Continuous integration and delivery (CI/CD) pipelines push frequent updates to xApps and network functions. Classical certificate lifetimes and revocation models cannot match this cadence, requiring agile or on-demand re-attestation.
Energy variability	O-DUs and O-RUs operate under diverse compute and power envelopes. PQC increases CPU cycles and memory footprints; without adaptive scaling, these nodes may exceed thermal or energy budgets.
Multi-vendor interoperability	O-RAN deployments combine hardware and software from different vendors. PQC adoption will occur unevenly across interfaces and versions, demanding backwards-compatible hybrid cryptography and negotiated capability discovery.

These constraints make a full PQ replacement unrealistic in early 6G phases, reinforcing the need for hybrid and phased PQC migration strategies [14]. *Hybrid deployment*, combining classical and PQ primitives within the same protocol (e.g., ECDHE + ML-KEM for TLS 1.3, ECDSA + ML-DSA for authentication), allows incremental hardening while preserving interoperability and timing compliance. Hybrid schemes ensure continuity of service when only subsets of nodes support PQC, and they offer measurable rollback paths during field validation. The following section maps where such a hybrid insertion is most feasible across the identity, control, and runtime layers of the O-RAN architecture.

III. PROPOSED LAYERED TRUST ARCHITECTURE

Quantum-resilient security in O-RAN requires a trust architecture that evolves without disrupting existing 5G operations. Rather than a single cryptographic transition, we propose a *layered trust model* aligned with O-RAN's functional split: (i) identity and root-of-trust, (ii) control and orchestration, and (iii) runtime execution. Each layer introduces hybrid capabilities incrementally, allowing quantum-safe mechanisms

Fig. 2. High-level Overview of the Proposed Architecture

to coexist with legacy components and maintaining interoperability across multi-vendor environments throughout the migration period. Figure 2 conceptually depicts these layers and their trust anchors.

A. Identity and Root-of-Trust Layer

This foundational layer anchors all cryptographic credentials within the SMO framework. It introduces a *hybrid certificate hierarchy*, where each certificate or token combines a classical and a PQ signature (e.g., ECDSA + ML-DSA). This design enables immediate verification by legacy entities while allowing PQ validation by upgraded components. Attestation reports, firmware integrity proofs, and lifecycle management events can be signed using PQ algorithms to ensure forward security of audit trails and onboarding flows.

Lifecycle operations, including xApp registration, RIC container updates, or DU image deployment, are validated through PQ signatures stored in the SMO's secure registry. However, interoperability remains ensured through classical fallback paths, so that existing Certificate Authorities (CAs) and orchestration APIs can continue operating during phased migration. This hybrid trust anchor effectively forms the *quantum root of trust* for the broader O-RAN ecosystem, while preserving continuity with the existing PKI infrastructure defined by O-RAN WG11.

B. Control and Orchestration Layer

The control and orchestration layer governs non-real-time and near-real-time management traffic, including A1 and E2 interfaces, policy updates, and telemetry feedback. Here, every control-plane session can transparently employ *hybrid key establishment*, for example, combining ECDHE and ML-KEM within TLS 1.3 or IPsec to achieve dual security guarantees.

When both endpoints support a hybrid implementation, classical and PQ primitives are combined within a single session to derive a shared symmetric key using a Key Derivation Function (KDF). Otherwise, standard capability negotiation triggers a fallback to classical cryptography, preserving interoperability during phased deployment.

This hybrid negotiation model allows operators to perform PQ upgrades gradually, staging them per interface or vendor domain without halting interoperability. Certificate validation retains backward compatibility since the hybrid certificates from the identity layer carry both signature types. Moreover, control-plane protocols such as NETCONF and gRPC can integrate PQC through their underlying transport layers without modifying orchestration semantics. This layer, therefore, represents the most practical entry point for quantum-safe hardening across heterogeneous vendor deployments.

C. Runtime Execution Layer

The runtime layer encompasses the near-real-time and real-time execution domains of O-RAN, including RIC applications, O-CU/O-DU components, and O-FH communication.

Security here focuses on maintaining deterministic timing rather than introducing new cryptographic delays. Given the timing constraints identified in Section II, PQ operations are confined to pre-runtime phases such as onboarding and session establishment. This design assumes that control-plane sessions are relatively long-lived, allowing the computational overhead of PQ-based key establishment and authentication to be amortized over multiple control-loop cycles, without impacting runtime execution.

Each RIC application (xApp or rApp) receives a revocable and traceable trust binding, derived from the hybrid identity layer, which authorizes its execution within the RIC sandbox. Runtime monitoring ensures that only verified components

TABLE III
PHASED MIGRATION ROADMAP TO QUANTUM-RESILIENT O-RAN

Phase	Timeline	Focus & Key Actions	Target Domains
1. Crypto-Agile Foundations	Current – 2026	Inventory crypto; Deploy agile APIs; Test hybrid certificates in labs.	SMO, Non-RT RIC (Testbeds)
2. Selective Hybrid Control	2026 – 2028	Activate hybrid TLS/IPsec (ECDHE+ML-KEM) for management and orchestration.	SMO ↔ RIC, O-CU (Control-Plane)
3. Full PQC at the Edge	2028 – 2031	Deploy PQC-only for edge control; Use hardware acceleration; Retire classical roots.	Near-RT RIC, O-CU/O-DU, xApps
4. End-to-End PQC & NTN	2031+	Full PQC across all domains; Integrate with Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN).	End-to-End, Terrestrial & NTN

participate in control loops. Under this architectural model, PQ operations are therefore excluded from the 10 ms–1 s near-real-time scheduling window, ensuring predictable control-loop performance.

This division of responsibility isolates high-latency PQ primitives from time-critical paths, enabling predictable performance even on resource-constrained DUs and RUs. The runtime layer, therefore, achieves quantum resilience primarily through verified provenance and revocable trust links rather than direct cryptographic enforcement. This separation also ensures that variations in hardware capability primarily affect non-runtime phases, preserving deterministic behavior even in heterogeneous and resource-constrained deployments.

D. Implementation Considerations

This design aligns with O-RAN WG11 and GSMA PQTN recommendations, offering a blueprint for introducing PQC into disaggregated network environments while maintaining compliance, continuity, and determinism.

Realising this architecture in practice requires coordinated modifications across both network and user domains. On the network side, O-RAN components, such as the SMO, RICs, O-CU/O-DU/O-RU, must support PQ-enabled protocols as well as extended certificate handling, including hybrid key formats and dual-signature verification. O-RAN interfaces (e.g., O1, A1, and E2) must accommodate PQ-capable authentication and key exchange, along with updated orchestration and policy mechanisms for managing hybrid cryptographic modes.

On the user side, endpoints and associated management systems must support PQ-capable cryptographic libraries, certificate validation mechanisms, and compatibility with hybrid or PQ-only trust models. This includes handling larger key and certificate sizes, as well as maintaining interoperability with legacy systems during transitional deployment phases.

IV. MIGRATION ROADMAP

Quantum-resilient transformation of O-RAN must progress in phases aligned with standards maturity, vendor readiness, and hardware refresh cycles. Table III and the following discussion summarize a pragmatic four-phase roadmap extending from the current pre-deployment stage to full PQ operation in 6G and Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN). This is also illustrated in Figure 3. Each phase maintains backward compatibility through hybrid cryptography, ensuring that service continuity and deterministic timing are never compromised.

A. Phase 1 (Current – 2026): Establish Crypto-Agile Foundations

The first phase focuses on *crypto-agility* rather than immediate PQ performance. Operators deploy algorithm-independent APIs and configuration interfaces inside the SMO and RIC components, allowing cryptographic primitives to be replaced or composed without service interruption. This includes:

- inventorying all cryptographic dependencies across O1/O2/A1/E2 and fronthaul links,
- extending PKI systems to support hybrid certificate formats (e.g., X.509 with dual signatures), and
- integrating PQ-ready libraries such as OpenSSL-OQS in testbed environments.

The objective is functional readiness and vendor awareness, not yet production deployment. Performance metrics gathered here establish baselines for later comparison.

B. Phase 2 (2026 – 2028): Selective Activation in Control-Plane Trust Channels

During this phase, PQC and hybrid algorithms become active in control and orchestration channels with manageable latency budgets (e.g., SMO–RIC–CU signalling). TLS 1.3 and IPsec sessions can adopt hybrid ECDHE+ML-KEM key exchanges and dual-signature certificates without affecting fronthaul determinism. The Non-RT RIC and SMO thus act as the pilot domains for quantum-safe migration. Certification authorities are upgraded to issue hybrid credentials, while classical verification remains supported for interoperability with unmodified nodes. Cross-vendor testing within O-RAN PlugFests and GSMA PQTN trials validates compatibility and helps refine latency and energy models.

C. Phase 3 (2028 – 2031): RAN Control and Edge Execution Become Fully PQ

In this phase, PQC extends toward the edge. Near-RT RIC control loops, O-CU/O-DU interfaces, and distributed edge clouds begin to rely exclusively on PQ key-establishment and signature algorithms. Hardware acceleration (e.g., RISC-V vector or FPGA co-processors) mitigates latency overheads. Runtime attestation of xApps and rApps uses PQ signatures exclusively, enabling revocable and traceable trust bindings described in Section III. Operators gradually retire classical root certificates, though hybrid fallback remains available for roaming and legacy equipment. By 2031, most terrestrial O-RAN domains will achieve full PQ compliance.

Fig. 3. PQC Migration Roadmap for O-RAN

D. Phase 4 (2031 and Beyond): End-to-End PQC for Multi-Domain and NTN Environments

The final phase integrates quantum-safe mechanisms end-to-end across terrestrial, aerial, and non-terrestrial (NTN) segments. All trust anchors are PQ, and hybrid support becomes optional rather than mandatory. Cross-domain orchestration, between O-RAN, transport, and core networks, relies on unified PQ certificate chains and quantum-resilient identity federation. NTN links may additionally combine PQC with Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) for high-assurance control channels. Sustainability becomes a central KPI, with PQ-optimized energy profiles mandated for all edge hardware.

This phased roadmap aligns with the GSMA PQTN and O-RAN WG11 recommendations, offering operators and vendors a realistic trajectory from today's crypto-agile foundations to fully quantum-resilient, standards-compliant 6G networks.

V. PERFORMANCE AND COST EVALUATION

Post-quantum migration influences O-RAN components in different ways because ML-KEM and ML-DSA have distinct computational and bandwidth profiles compared to classical ECDHE and ECDSA. Their effects therefore manifest at the system level, in handshake latency, CPU load, memory consumption, and certificate size, rather than at the level of individual primitives. To provide a realistic view of deployment impact, we derive normalized cost estimates from recent measurements of ML-KEM and ML-DSA across multiple platform classes and apply them to the identity, control, and runtime layers defined in Section III. Table IV summarizes the resulting layer-wise overheads for classical, PQ-only, and hybrid protection modes.

Note that the latency factors discussed in this section model cryptographic processing overhead only. In practical O-RAN deployments, network round-trip time typically dominates absolute control-plane setup latency. However, PQ overhead becomes more substantial under conditions of high session churn, such as frequent rekeying, short-lived connections, or large numbers of concurrently instantiated xApps. In such cases, the cost of repeated cryptographic handshakes may accumulate and increase latency and energy consumption, especially for hybrid systems that need the processing of

dual cryptographic material. These effects may lead to non-linear scaling of overhead, which is not fully captured by the static multipliers used in this analysis. As a result, the reported figures should be taken as approximate average-case estimations rather than precise projections for all deployment conditions.

A. Estimation Methodology

The normalized performance values in Table IV are derived from recent empirical measurements of PQ primitives and qualitative guidance from telecom migration frameworks. Our system-level estimates rely on two sources:

- (1) the benchmark study by Abbasi *et al.* [15], which evaluates ML-KEM and ML-DSA across heterogeneous hardware using OpenSSL-OQS and reports end-to-end TLS 1.3 handshake costs for classical, PQ-only, and hybrid modes; and
- (2) GSMA PQ.03 [10], which provides operator-facing expectations on memory, bandwidth, and deployment feasibility of ML-KEM / ML-DSA in 5G- and 6G-class systems.

The normalized overhead factors presented in this section are based on empirical benchmarks from SMO and RIC-class platforms, and should be interpreted as representative system-level estimates rather than hardware-independent values. In resource-constrained edge environments, such as O-DU and O-RU deployments, PQC operations may incur higher relative computational overhead, particularly in the absence of hardware acceleration. However, in the proposed architecture, these operations are confined to onboarding, session establishment, and lifecycle events, and are therefore excluded from time-critical runtime control loops. As a result, even under worst-case hardware conditions, the impact on deterministic control-loop latency remains bounded under the stated assumptions, while increased cost is primarily reflected in setup latency and energy consumption rather than runtime behavior.

For reference, empirical studies report that ML-KEM-based TLS handshakes introduce an additional latency of approximately 0.4–0.7 ms compared to classical TLS [15]. When compared to near-real-time control-loop periods (10 ms–1 s), this overhead can be effectively amortized across multiple control cycles in typical deployments with persistent sessions,

supporting the architectural assumption that PQ operations remain outside the critical runtime path.

B. Handshake and CPU cost

Abbasi *et al.* measure the following average TLS 1.3 handshake latencies using ML-KEM at NIST Level 3 on a server-class platform [15]:

$$T_{\text{classical}} \approx 1.8 \text{ ms}, \quad T_{\text{PQ-only}} \approx 2.2 \text{ ms}, \quad T_{\text{hybrid}} \approx 2.5 \text{ ms}.$$

These correspond to normalized factors of approximately $1.2\times$ (PQ-only) and $1.40\times$ (hybrid) relative to classical TLS and represent conservative illustrative multipliers. Absolute overheads depend on the underlying CPU class, cryptographic implementation, selected security level, and whether cryptographic operations are amortized over long-lived sessions. We apply these ratios directly to the control and orchestration layer, where TLS/IPsec handshakes dominate session setup cost.

C. Signature and attestation cost

For ML-DSA, Abbasi *et al.* report signing and verification times in the same order of magnitude as ECDSA on server- and laptop-class hardware, with higher overhead on edge devices [15]. Because identity and attestation operations are executed on SMO-class and controller hardware, we normalise the CPU impact again to $1.2\times$ for PQ-only and $1.4\times$ for hybrid (which requires verifying both ML-DSA and ECDSA signatures).

D. Memory and bandwidth

Abbasi *et al.* also report memory usage and key/ciphertext sizes for ML-KEM and ML-DSA. At NIST Level 3, ML-KEM public keys (≈ 1184 bytes) and ciphertexts (≈ 1088 bytes) exceed ECDHE by several hundred bytes, and ML-DSA signatures (≈ 2.7 kB) are larger than ECDSA signatures, resulting in moderate increases in handshake packet size and certificate chain lengths. GSMA PQ.03 classifies these increases as acceptable on core and RAN control hardware, but highlights the need for careful budgeting on O-DU/O-RU nodes. We therefore apply conservative normalized multipliers of 10% memory increase for PQ-only and 15–20% for hybrid due to dual-signature chains.

E. Runtime execution assumptions

Following the architectural restrictions in Section III, we assume no ML-KEM or ML-DSA operations inside the 10 ms–1 s near-real-time control loop. PQ costs are therefore limited to onboarding, image verification, and periodic re-attestation. Normalized estimates of $1.2\times$ (PQ-only) and $1.3\times$ (hybrid) reflect this bounded scope.

F. Comparative assessment of cryptographic approaches for O-RAN

Figure 4 summarizes the relative trade-offs between classical, PQ-only, and hybrid cryptography across six dimensions that directly influence O-RAN adoption.

Security strength favors PQ-only and hybrid modes because ML-KEM and ML-DSA resist quantum attacks, while classical schemes provide only short-term protection. Interoperability is highest for classical cryptography and hybrid schemes, since hybrid certificates and handshakes remain compatible with legacy RAN nodes; PQ-only options require uniform vendor support. Performance reflects the normalized overheads measured in Table III, where PQ-only incurs moderate CPU and bandwidth increases and hybrid modes introduce the highest handshake and attestation cost. Implementation complexity grows from classical to PQ-only to hybrid, because hybrid deployments require dual certificate chains, dual signature verification, and extended PKI logic. Operational cost captures the additional memory ($\approx 10\text{--}20\%$), larger certificates, and increased control-plane packet sizes that accumulate during migration. Maturity is highest for classical cryptography, intermediate for hybrid schemes (already supported in OpenSSL-OQS and PQ-IPsec prototypes), and still developing for PQ-only deployments. This multi-axis comparison provides a fast, operator-oriented view of where each approach fits into the summarized migration phases.

Fig. 4. Comparison of Classical, PQ-Only, and Hybrid Cryptography for O-RAN

VI. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The presented layered trust architecture shows that hybrid deployment offers a practical bridge toward quantum-resilient O-RAN, but several ecosystem dependencies remain. The standardization timeline continues to evolve: NIST has finalized ML-KEM and ML-DSA, while ETSI QSC and GSMA PQTN are shaping migration profiles. The next step is their translation into concrete O-RAN specifications, followed by vendor-level integration cycles aligned with hardware refresh periods.

TABLE IV
NORMALIZED OVERHEAD OF CLASSICAL, PQ-ONLY, AND HYBRID SECURITY PER O-RAN LAYER (ILLUSTRATIVE, BASED ON ML-KEM / ML-DSA)

Layer	Mode	CPU Cost	Relative Latency	Resource Impact (Energy / Memory / Bandwidth)
Identity	Classical	1.0×	Baseline	Baseline memory and bandwidth; standard ECDSA-based PKI and certificate chains.
	PQ-only	1.2×	≈ 10–20% longer per attestation (SMO-class nodes)	Substantially larger ML-DSA public keys and signatures compared to ECDSA; moderate certificate-chain size increase due to PQ material; bandwidth impact is negligible as attestation is infrequent and non-runtime-critical.
	Hybrid	1.4×	≈ 30–40% longer per attestation	Dual ECDSA and ML-DSA public keys and signatures increase certificate size and storage requirements; certificate-chain growth confined to PKI/SMO components; bandwidth increase is limited to attestation and onboarding phases.
Control	Classical	1.0×	Baseline handshake latency	Baseline packet sizes in TLS/IPsec control-plane sessions.
	PQ-only	1.2×	≈ 20–25% longer cryptographic handshake processing	Additional CPU cost from ML-KEM encapsulation and decapsulation; ML-KEM public keys and ciphertexts (on the order of ~1 kB each) increase handshake message size; one-time bandwidth overhead per session, with no impact on steady-state traffic.
	Hybrid	1.4×	≈ 35–40% longer cryptographic handshake processing	Combined transmission of classical ECDHE and ML-KEM key material; handshake bandwidth increases by approximately 1–2 kB per session; CPU overhead dominated by ML-KEM operations; symmetric-key dataplane traffic is unaffected after session establishment.
Runtime	Classical	1.0×	Baseline	Baseline resource usage in 10 ms–1 s near-RT and non-RT control loops.
	PQ-only	1.2×	No impact on runtime loop latency	PQ operations confined to onboarding, key establishment, and periodic re-attestation; moderate increase in CPU and memory usage during these phases; no additional bandwidth or latency impact during steady-state runtime operation.
	Hybrid	1.3×	No impact on runtime loop latency; slightly longer onboarding	Verification of both ML-DSA and ECDSA signatures during onboarding and re-attestation; increased CPU and memory usage relative to PQ-only; runtime control and data-plane traffic remain unaffected, with negligible energy impact.

Initial proofs-of-concept, PQ-TLS 1.3, hybrid IPsec, and PQ-augmented JWTs, demonstrate technical feasibility, but require systematic evaluation in O-RAN PlugFests and RIC application ecosystems. As PQC implementations improve and hardware acceleration becomes available, hybrid and PQ-only modes must be reassessed within the constraints of real-time RAN behavior. In this context, the proposed architectural separation of PQ operations from near-real-time control loops should be understood as a design guideline rather than a strict system requirement. This assumption is valid when cryptographic operations such as key establishment, attestation, and certificate validation are performed during session setup or lifecycle events, and when control-plane sessions remain relatively long-lived.

As O-RAN evolves towards software-driven 6G architectures, it may lead to high session churn, frequent rekeying, and tighter integration of security mechanisms within control loops. PQ cryptographic operations may extend to near-real-time domains, potentially affecting latency and determinism. To address these challenges, hardware acceleration, optimized PQ implementations, and revised control-plane designs are required.

Hybrid cryptographic deployment also introduces chal-

lenges in certificate management and interoperability. Dual-signature certificate chains increase storage and control-plane overhead, while revocation and trust anchor rollover become more complex in multi-vendor environments. These aspects highlight the need for standardized and scalable hybrid PKI mechanisms to ensure consistent and disruption-free migration.

Scalability in large-scale and dense deployments is primarily determined by how distributed O-RAN components manage cryptographic state, certificate lifecycle operations, and control-plane signaling. Because the proposed architecture limits most PQC-related processing to identity provisioning, control-plane configuration, and lifecycle events, steady-state runtime behavior is largely unaffected. Nonetheless, dense deployments with a large number of nodes, xApps, and rApps may result in increased overhead. Scalable certificate management, long-lived secure sessions, hierarchical orchestration, and hardware-assisted cryptographic processing all play important roles in maintaining operational efficiency in such environments.

The migration plan presented in this paper is also consistent with larger PQC transition initiatives, such as the European Union's (EU) coordinated roadmap for PQC. The

EU roadmap takes a phased approach, aiming to complete PQC transformation for high-risk use cases by 2030 and broader system migration by 2035. The strategy provided in this paper is consistent with these principles as it focuses on crypto-agility, hybrid deployments, and a gradual transition to PQ-only mechanisms.

A full real-time evaluation in an integrated O-RAN testbed remains an important direction for future validation, particularly as PQ-enabled protocol stacks and multi-vendor interoperability mature. Future research should address three main gaps: energy-aware PQC integration for edge devices; scalable PQ attestation and lifecycle management; and novel trust models, including PQC-friendly zero-knowledge proofs and accountable provenance for distributed RIC ecosystems. These directions are essential for achieving quantum-safe multi-vendor O-RAN deployments beyond 2030.

VII. CONCLUSION

The proposed framework enables system-level design decisions for PQC integration in O-RAN, bridging the gap between high-level standardization guidance and deployment-oriented architectural constraints. By structuring trust anchors, control-plane protection, and runtime execution into a layered model, we identified where hybrid and PQC-only mechanisms can be introduced without violating timing or interoperability constraints. The accompanying cost analysis shows that overhead is manageable when confined to identity and orchestration layers. Combined with a phased migration plan, these insights provide a practical foundation for industry adoption and future standardization.

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